

INTRODUCTION TO THE COST ACTION 6G-PHYSEC

Physical layer security for trustworthy and resilient 6G systems
(6G-PHYSEC)

Start Date: 26/09/2023

End Date: 25/09/2027

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European Cooperation in Science & Technology (COST)

COST provides funding for research coordination and capacity building activities

COST is not funding research itself, but pooling resources and research results by networking

Source: COST

Our Focus

Source: 6G foundations, Ericsson White Paper GFTL-20:001402 Feb. 2022

COST Action 6G-PHYSEC (CA22168)

ACTION OVERVIEW

Main objective: Address key security challenges in future generations of wireless and cyber-physical systems by proposing novel, context-aware, intelligent, sustainable, and adaptive security controls at all layers, with a particular focus on the physical layer (PHY), thus enabling trustworthiness and resilience in 6G systems

Kickoff: 26.09.2023

No. of COST countries: 27

No. of ITC countries: 14

No. of international partner: 1

No. of MC members: 47

No. of approved WG members: 76

*Data on 05.01.2024

MC: Management Committee

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the COST Action website. It includes the COST logo (European Cooperation in Science & Technology) and navigation links for COST Actions, Funding, COST Academy, and About. A green 'Open call Fund your network' button is visible. The main content area features the title 'CA22168 - Physical layer security for trustworthy and resilient 6G systems (6G-PHYSEC)' and a 'Downloads' link. The background has a red-to-orange gradient with a target icon.

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Description	Management Committee	Main Contacts and Leadership	Working Groups and Membership
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Description

Other than simply inheriting vulnerabilities from the previous generations, 6G will face new threat vectors, including in the radio and massive Internet of things (IoT) domains. The COST Action 6G-PHYSEC will thus focus on creating a European network of academia and industry experts that helps the development of trustworthy and resilient 6G that can instill trust, secure communications and privacy by proposing novel physical layer security (PLS) solutions.

The premise of 6G-PHYSEC is that in 6G, intelligent and adaptive security controls are needed at all layers, with adaptation enabled by the distillation of semantics and context. The focus of this Action is on exploiting the characteristics of physical phenomena to provide security functionalities; PLS can

Action Details

- MoU - 078/23
- CSO Approval date - 12/05/2023
- Start date - 26/09/2023
- End date - 25/09/2027

Organizational Structure

WG. 1 Trustworthy 6G

- Focuses on trustworthiness-by-design of the 6G system, by considering security, privacy, and trust.
- Identify attack models and requirements for trustworthiness according to different 6G user scenarios.
- Identify KPIs and KVIs. Define trust models, metrics, and test procedures to evaluate trust in 6G systems.
- Work for building a framework to guarantee trustworthiness in 6G systems.

WG. 2 Intelligent and Resilient Systems

- Definition of resilience in the context of Physical Layer and 6G
- The use of AI to understand the security and privacy state of the communication system
- Methods to adapt the communication system to react to challenges
- Methods to improve general resilience to challenges
- Testbed infrastructures to evaluate proposed methods

WG. 3 - Quantum resistant security

- Identify possible threats deriving from quantum information technology against physical layer security techniques, and relevant countermeasures.
- Identify possible vulnerabilities to quantum computer-equipped attackers in 5G+ networks.
- Identify application scenarios that might not support post-quantum cryptography (e.g., due to constrained devices and resources), which may benefit from physical layer security for achieving quantum-resistance.
- Look for intersecting research lines between post-quantum cryptography and physical layer security.

WG. 4 Scalable and Sustainable Security

- Sustainable and scalable PLS solutions for low energy consumption, low energy footprint, low latencies while scaling with number of devices
- Model the total energy consumption including feedback, signaling, overhead as well as complexity of transceiver and algorithms
- Analysis and design of optimized PLS protocols exploiting recent technologies in 6G, e.g., RIS, THz, massive and extreme MIMO (with WG.1)
- Algorithms and protocols should be adaptive to meet the security and communications demand in the best way: Pareto optimality (with WG.2)
- Recommendation for parameter choices depending on scenario and use case in close discussion with industry, consumers, and policy makers
- Usability for end-users is considered by design (with WG.5)

WG. 5 Experiments and demonstrations

- Bridging the theoretical outcomes of WGs to real-world solutions, engaging in a collaborative exchange with the latter to establish a practical framework for security.
- Promoting interconnection and joint design within all layers of the communication protocol stack to enhance security and trustworthiness, leveraging PLS techniques.
- Identifying and promoting the development of real-time experiments, demonstrations, and proof-of-concept testbeds to draw attention to the potential of PLS.
- Persuade industry and policy makers to actively participate and grasp the significance of PLS techniques for resilience and trustworthiness in the upcoming 6G era.
- Fostering an OpenAccess platform for the community to gather diverse datasets and shared code, encouraging collaborative exploration and study of PLS techniques

Initial activities

Workshop at IEEE GLOBECOM 2023 Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec. 2023

IEEE Global Communications Conference
4–8 December 2023 // Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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WS09: WORKSHOP ON ENABLING SECURITY, TRUST, AND PRIVACY IN 6G WIRELESS SYSTEMS

WS09: WORKSHOP ON ENABLING SECURITY, TRUST, AND PRIVACY IN 6G WIRELESS SYSTEMS

The IEEE Globecom Workshop on Enabling Security, Trust, and Privacy in 6G Wireless Systems will take place on 4th December 2023 in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. The objective of the workshop is to both foster and develop the ground-breaking technique to provide trustworthy and resilient wireless communications. In line with such objectives, original contributions are solicited in topics of interest to include, but not limited to, the following:

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Initial activities

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COST Action 6G-PHYSEC

COST Action CA22168 (6G-PHYSEC) - Physical layer security for trustworthy and resilient 6G systems

Brussels, Brussels Region, Belgium · [Contact Info](#)

120 followers · 85 connections

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Upcoming activities

MC-WG meeting (onsite) at University of Padova, Feb. 1- 2, 2024

MC-WG meeting (onsite) at Aalto University, jointly with COST INTERACT, Jun. 17th – 19th, 2024

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DI PADOVA

*Regular WG meetings (online): every 2-3 months

Upcoming activities

Other activities (non exhaustive list):

- Training school in Sep. 2024
- Meeting with other COST Actions, e.g., INTERACT
- Support Short-term scientific mission
- Tutorials

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- Twitter(X): https://twitter.com/6G_PhySec

Thank you for your
attention

